

Studies on Conductance of Uranyl Soaps

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Specific conductance of uranyl soaps in dimethylformamide indicates two critical micelle concentrations CMC(I) and CMC(II). The value of CMC(II) decreases with the increase in chainlength of the soap, whereas CMC(I) does not vary at all. The results show that the soaps behave as simple electrolyte. The molar conductance at infinite dilution (μ) and dissociation constant (K) of these soaps have been evaluated

SEVERAL reviews¹⁻⁸ exist on the methods of preparation, characteristics and structure of alkali, alkaline earth and transition metal soaps but the fundamental characteristics of lanthanide and actinide soaps⁹⁻¹² have not been investigated systematically so far although these soaps have found increasing applications in industries. The present work deals with the study of the properties of the solutions of uranyl soaps (caprylate and caprate) in dimethylformamide (DMF) by using conductivity measurements with a view to determine the CMC and study the nature of uranyl soaps in solutions.

Experimental

Uranyl soaps were prepared by the direct metathesis of the corresponding potassium soaps with the required amount of aqueous solution of uranyl nitrate. The soaps were purified by recrystallisation from dimethylformamide and analysed for elemental contents. The reproducibility of the results was checked by preparing two samples of the soaps under similar condition.

A Toshniwal CL 01 10A digital conductivity meter and a dipping type conductivity cell with platinized electrode were used for measuring the conductance of the soap solutions. All measurements were made at $40 \pm 0.05^\circ$.

Results and Discussion

Specific conductance : The molar conductance (μ) of the solutions of uranyl soaps (caprylate and caprate) involves the effects of both the simple ions and micelles and so the specific conductance (k) of the soap solutions has been plotted against the soap concentration (C) to determine the CMC of the soap. The specific conductance of the solutions of uranyl soaps in dimethylformamide increases with the increase in soap concentration (Table 1). The plots of specific conductance vs soap concentrations (Fig. 1) are characterised by two breaks at concentrations corresponding to the formation of

Fig 1. Plots of specific conductance (k) vs concentration (C): (○) caprylate and (○) caprate.

ionic and neutral micelles in these soap solutions. The increase of specific conductance with increasing concentrations of soap in very dilute solutions below 0.033 M is mainly due to the fact that the soaps behave as simple electrolytes in very dilute solutions and are considerably ionised into uranyl ions (UO_2^{2+}) and fatty acid anions ($C_7H_{15}COO^-$ or $C_8H_{17}COO^-$ in case of caprylate or caprate, respectively). At an appreciable concentration of soaps (0.033 M), where the plots of specific conductance vs soap concentration show first break, *i.e.* CMC(I), the anions begin to aggregate to form ionic micelles. It is suggested that the soaps are considerably ionised in dilute solutions (below 0.033 M) and are largely present in the form of ionic micelles at moderate concentrations [between CMC(I) and CMC(II) and there is an increasing formation of larger particles (neutral or lamellar micelles)]. These particles have laminated structure of layers of undissociated molecules of soaps and are charged as a result of attachment of ions just like an ordinary colloidal particle.

The results show that CMC(I) is independent of the chainlength of soap and it appears that the

TABLE 1—CONDUCTIVITY OF URANYL SOAPS IN DMF AT 40±0.05°

C × 10 ² mole dm ⁻³	Specific conductance (k) × 10 ⁴ Ω ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	Molar conductance (μ) Ω ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	log μ	1/μ × 10 ³ Ω cm mol	μ ² C ²	K × 10 ³
Caprylate						
1.72	4.22	24.53	1.389 7	4.08	0.178	5.1
1.78	4.34	24.38	1.387 0	4.10	0.178	5.1
1.85	4.47	24.16	1.383 1	4.14	0.200	5.1
1.92	4.59	23.91	1.378 6	4.18	0.211	5.1
2.00	4.74	23.70	1.374 7	4.22	0.225	5.2
2.27	5.18	22.82	1.358 3	4.38	0.268	5.1
2.38	5.32	22.52	1.352 6	4.44	0.287	5.1
2.50	5.55	22.20	1.346 4	4.50	0.308	5.1
2.63	5.77	21.94	1.341 2	4.56	0.333	5.2
2.78	5.99	21.55	1.333 4	4.64	0.359	5.2
2.94	6.22	21.16	1.325 5	4.72	0.387	5.2
Caprate						
1.72	3.95	22.96	1.361 0	4.36	0.156	7.4
1.78	4.06	22.81	1.358 1	4.38	0.165	7.4
1.85	4.17	22.54	1.353 0	4.44	0.174	7.1
1.92	4.28	22.29	1.348 1	4.49	0.183	6.9
2.00	4.42	22.10	1.344 4	4.52	0.195	6.9
2.27	4.87	21.45	1.331 4	4.66	0.237	6.9
2.38	5.02	21.09	1.324 0	4.74	0.252	6.9
2.50	5.21	20.84	1.318 9	4.80	0.271	6.7
2.63	5.40	20.53	1.312 4	4.87	0.292	6.8
2.78	5.61	20.18	1.304 9	4.96	0.315	6.7
2.94	5.83	19.83	1.297 4	5.04	0.340	6.7

anions begin to aggregate to form ionic micelles at almost the same concentration in dimethylformamide for uranyl caprylate and caprate. It may be pointed out that CMC(I) is not observed when it is determined by viscosity and spectrophotometric measurements. However, the values (caprylate, 0.07 M; caprate, 0.06 M) of CMC(II) decrease with the increasing chainlength of soap and are in agreement with those obtained from viscosity and spectrophotometry.

Molar conductance and dissociation constant: The molar conductance (μ) of the solutions of uranyl soaps (caprylate and caprate) in DMF decreases with the increase in soap concentrations (Table 1). The decrease in molar conductance may be due to the combined effects of ionic atmosphere, solvation of ions and decrease of mobility and ionisation with the formation of micelles. The plots of molar conductance (μ) vs square-root of soap concentration (C^{1/2}) are not linear which indicates that the Debye-Hückel-Onsager equation is not applicable to these soap solutions and the limiting molar conductance (μ₀) for these soap solutions can not be obtained by the usual extrapolation method. The plots of log μ vs log C for the solutions of these soaps in DMF show an intersection of two straight lines at a point which corresponds to CMC(I). The behaviour of these plots below and above CMC(I) may be described by the equation,

$$\log \mu = A + B \log C \quad (1)$$

where, A and B are constants. The values of A and B obtained from the intercept and slope of the plots

of log μ vs log C, are recorded in Table 2. The comparison of results show that the values of A are

TABLE 2—VALUES OF CONSTANTS A AND B FOR URANYL SOAPS

Constant	Caprylate		Caprate	
	Below CMC(I)	Above CMC(I)	Below CMC(I)	Above CMC(I)
A	0.88	0.68	0.95	0.60
B	0.30	0.45	0.25	0.45

higher below CMC(I) whereas the values of B are lower below CMC(I). It is found that the values of both the constants are almost independent of the chainlength of the soap.

Since the soaps behave as a simple electrolyte, the expression for the dissociation of uranyl soaps can be developed in Ostwald's manner. If C is the concentration of uranyl soaps and α is the degree of dissociation, the equivalent concentrations of different species can be written as

where R is C₇H₁₅COO⁻ or C₉H₁₉COO⁻ for caprylate and caprate, respectively. The dissociation constant (K) can be expressed as

$$K = \frac{[UO_2^{2+}][R^-]^2}{[R_2(UO_2)]}$$

$$= C\alpha(2C\alpha)^2 / C(1-\alpha) = 4C^2\alpha^3 / (1-\alpha) \quad (2)$$

In dilute solutions ionic concentrations will be low and so the interionic effects may be treated as

negligible. Therefore, the dilute soap solutions do not deviate appreciably from ideal behaviour and the activities of ions can be taken as almost equal to the concentrations. The degree of dissociation (α) may be replaced by the conductance ratio, μ/μ_0 , where μ is the molar conductance at finite concentration and μ_0 is the limiting molar conductance at infinite dilution. On substituting the value of α and rearranging equation (2), we obtain,

$$\mu^2 C^2 = \frac{K\mu_0^2}{4\mu} - \frac{K\mu_0^2}{4} \quad (3)$$

The values of K and μ_0 can be obtained from the slope, $K\mu_0^2/4$, and intercept, $-K\mu_0^2/4$, of the plots of $\mu^2 C^2$ vs $1/\mu$ for dilute soap solutions. The values of limiting molar conductance (μ_0) are 28.7 and 25.8, and dissociation constant are 5.8×10^{-8} and 6.3×10^{-8} for caprylate and caprate, respectively. The values of limiting molar conductance and dissociation constant exhibit small change with increasing chainlength of the soap from caprylate to caprate. The values of dissociation constant (K) below CMC, calculated by using equation (2) and assuming the degree of dissociation as equal to the conductance ratio μ/μ_0 , are recorded in Table 1.

The results show that these soaps behave as simple electrolytes in very dilute solutions and the

conductance results can be explained on the basis of Ostwald's formula.

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